

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D1.7 RP2 UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this deliverable, an update of the MAPWORMS Data Management Plan (DMP) at project month 30 (M30) is reported. The MAPWORMS DMP aims to define the management steps and protocols to inform and guide the researchers involved in the project, in properly managing their data and software. The MAPWORMS Team recognizes the importance of effective data management of the research data and the development of a robust DMP in anticipation of planned research activities. Following the Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP Template,^[1] the MAPWORMS DMP includes information about the handling, collection, processing, and generation of research data, the applied methodologies and standards, the procedures for sharing and making the data open access and the curation and preservation of the data.

This is the updated version of the MAPWORMS DMP, which should be considered a living document that can be revised and will be matured based on the progress achieved through the lifecycle of the project. In this version the main updates include the following:

- ✓ *Update of biological data collected regarding the marine annelid fauna occurring along the Salento Peninsula coastline (Italy) through two sources: from literature data and from sampling events.*
- ✓ *Standardisation of data and metadata collected according to Darwin Core Standards.*
- ✓ *Update of Micro CT metadata records.*
- ✓ *Definition of the controlled vocabularies used with examples given according to provided information.*
- ✓ *Change of the definition of patent data to patent-search data, as WP6 is referred to the search for existing patent data, rather than the generation of new data that will potentially turn out from all technical WPs of the project.*
- ✓ *Update of the [MAPWORMS community in Zenodo](#).*
- ✓ *Separation of the anatomical modelling data and update of its description.*
- ✓ *Standardisation of the different data types available in [Zenodo MAPWORMS community](#); according to MAPWORMS naming conventions presented in Table 2 and enrichment of metadata records in accordance with the Article 17 of the MAPWORMS grant agreement.*

1 INTRODUCTION

MAPWORMS project aims to design robots that are inspired by simplified forms of marine Annelida, able to perform tasks in response to environmental stimuli, thus adapting to the working environment with a shape-morphing strategy. Specifically, this project, intends to: 1) study the adaptation and plasticity of the marine Annelids body; 2) develop a mathematical model of Annelida plasticity and adaptation to the environment; 3) develop

smart soft materials embodying responsiveness, shape morphing, and self-healing capabilities; 4) develop bio-inspired modular shape morphing robots across scales.

As it is stated in the Description of Action (DoA) and specifically in Task 1.3, this DMP is a reference document for the Consortium, and it will outline how the research data collected or generated within the project activities will be handled during the project and it will remain in force after the end of the project. For this reason, the MAPWORMS DMP should be considered a living document that can be revised in accordance with the project achievements.

Since data gathering and curation are key factors, a Data Manager (DM) was appointed for the DMP handling during the MAPWORMS kick-off meeting, on the 13th of May 2022, in Pisa (Italy). Figure 1 presents the organizational structure of the MAPWORMS DMP. The DM defines the framework of data handling to inform and guide all participating partners in properly managing their data (and software). The DM is in contact with all partners - individually and as a group - throughout the project life in order to discuss and solve any possible difficulties in data sharing and publishing. In addition, the DM works closely with the Innovation Manager (IM) and the Innovation Management Board (IMB) for the appropriate handling of data and in particular of those related to the project results patenting.

Figure 1 Organizational structure of the MAPWORMS Data Management Plan.

This document is the first update of the MAPWORMS DMP and is related to all six WPs and in particular: WP1 - Project coordination, dissemination, and communication, WP2 - Ecological, taxonomical and morphological studies for selected species of marine Annelida, WP3 - Annelid shape-morphing modelling, WP4 - Smart stimuli-responsive hydrogels, WP5 - Morphing robots across scales, and WP6 - Robots testing towards application case studies and exploitation activities.

2 DATA SUMMARY

MAPWORMS data will be used to develop bio-inspired soft robots able to perform tasks in response to environmental stimuli. Specifically, the data generated and collected from WP2 will be relevant to annelid taxonomy, behavior, and ecology in order to provide the biological background for WPs 3, 4 and 5. Furthermore, data derived from the WP3 aim to develop theoretical and numerical tools for worm and robot modeling. Data generated by WP4 will be related to the development and characterization of stimuli-responsive DNA-based hydrogels that exhibit controlled stiffness functions, shape-memory, and self-healing properties. These data will be used in WP5 in order to develop a worm-inspired soft modular robot featured by shape morphing capabilities and responsiveness to environmental stimuli. Selected data will be used for WP6 in order to investigate potential applications and exploitation opportunities of the robot. Specifically, in the present document, the term 'data' refers to the following four main categories of information that will be used and/or produced during the project:

1. **Biological Data:** data collected through the described processes in WP2. This data category provides the solid biological background for WP3, WP4 and WP5, by using Annelida Phylum and its evolutionary patterns as a model and source of bioinspiration.
2. **Technical Data:** all data related to WP3, WP4, WP5 and partly WP6. In particular, the processes of Annelid shape-morphing modelling, stimuli-responsive materials and morphing robot design and characterization, as well as testing in advanced platforms for applications under analysis.
3. **Patent-search Data:** related to WP6, giving an overview on already available technologies that are patented in the field of research using methodology developed within the project.
4. **Dissemination Data:** information obtained through the MAPWORMS project through social media and its official website, as well as the scientific publications referring to the procedures and/or the results of the research conducted.

Table 1 presents an updated summary of the research domains and the data software, and data files that have been used and are expected to be used and produced by the participating partners of the MAPWORMS project. The basic information provided comes from the answers given by MAPWORMS partners when replying to the MAPWORMS Data Management Questionnaire (see ANNEX II), which was based on the questions of the Horizon 2020 FAIR Data Management Plan Template.^[1] This Questionnaire was sent to each partner on May 20th 2022, along with instructions, in order to collect information on the data they are going to collect and/or produce during the project and on potential preferences for handling their data. Furthermore, the table was updated based on the results that have been already produced up to September 2024.

Table 1 The research domains and the data formats and data files that have been produced or are expected to be produced by the participating partners of the MAPWORMS project.

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Research domain(s)	Data standards/ vocabularies and software/ tools used	Data file types
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data	biogeographic research, traits, taxonomy	Darwin Core standards, OBIS-ENV-DATA IPT (integrated publishing tool) (open source)	csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx, .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; .xml; .rff; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff)
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data	DNA sequencing	M2B3 Reporting Standard Read data: general (CRAM, BAM, Fastq) and platform specific (SFF, PacBio, Oxford Nanopore, CompleteGenomics) Assembled and annotated sequence data: flat file format (FASTA, XML), Multiple Sequence Alignment (MSA) formats	csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx, .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; SPSS, Stata, Sas, DDI XML, .sav; .dta; xml; .rff; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; .fas
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Morphological data	measurements, pictures, drawings		csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx, .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff),
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Behavioral data	videos, footages, ethograms		csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx, .txt; doc; .docx; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; MPEG-4 (.mp4), motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2)), AVI (.avi)
HCMR	Biological Data	Micro CT data	Micro CT images, digital images, videos,	micro-CTvlab, Slice-Drop (open source) CTVox, nRecon (commercial)	JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff), PNG (.png); MPEG-4 (.mp4), AVI (.avi); nifti (.nii)
HCMR	Biological Data	Morphological data	2D/3D analysis	CTAn, DataViewer softwares (commercial), Dragonfly software (Free licence for researchers with non-commercial activities/Commercial) Landmark (freeware)	csv; .xls; .xlsx, .txt, .obj; .stl

SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data	numbers, codes, software, mechanical simulations, images, movies	MATLAB (academic version), Solidworks (academic version), COMSOL (for a fee)	Datasheet (.csv, .xls, .xlsx, .txt); MATLAB (.m, .fig); Multiphysics (.mph); CAD (.stl); Drawings (.eps, .svg); JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg); PNG (.png); MPEG-4 (.mp4), AVI (.avi); pdf
VEXLUM	Technical Data	Laser characterization data	Datasheets	Power, wavelength, beam quality, 2D drawings	.pdf
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental data	synthesis and characterisation of stimuli-responsive hydrogels	Origin software ImageJ	xls; xlx; JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff), PNG (.png); .opj, .opju
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data	numbers, codes, software, mechanical simulations, images, movies	MATLAB (academic version), Arduino (open source) LabView (for a fee), Solidworks (academic version), COMSOL (for a fee), Instron (commercial), ImageJ (open source), Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (commercial), Force sensors (commercial), Tracker (open source)	Datasheet (.csv, .xls, .xlsx, .txt); MATLAB (.m, .fig); Multiphysics (.mph); CAD (.stl); Drawings (.eps, .svg); JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg); PNG (.png); MPEG-4 (.mp4), AVI (.avi); pdf
ACMIT	Technical Data	Anatomical modelling data	anatomical models (phantoms)	medical ontologies (such as SNOMED CT or OntoSPM), CAD software (Solidworks, Fusion), 3D Slicer (open source), Prusaslicer (open source)	docx, xlsx, txt, pdf, png, jpeg, stl, 3mf, gcode, step, f3d, sldprt, sldasm, nrrd, mml
ACMIT	Patent-search Data	patent lists	Soft robots for medical technology	Google Patent, Espacenet, Patoffice	pdf, xlsx, docx

All	Dissemination Data		presentation, article, 3D models for touchscreen monitor, micro-CT images and videos for mobile app etc.	D1.2_project handbook, project Grant Agreement Drishti and Drishti Prayog (open source)	JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg, TIFF (.tif, .tiff), PNG (.png); txt, .doc; .docx; pdf; html; MPEG-4 (.mp4), AVI (.avi); xml, .drishtiprayog
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DATA RE-USE

Concerning the reusing of any existing data, **CoNISMa** examined published literature about annelids along the Salento peninsula to mine historical distributional data. Furthermore, regarding molecular analyses and phylogenetic reconstructions, sequences deposited in online repositories will be used to compare with the newly obtained ones. **HCMR** has already examined the protocols and methods of annelids micro-CT scans created by the HCMR imaging laboratory, in order to guide the development of the new micro-CT methods for the MAPWORMS project. However, new scanning protocols have been created as the selected species needed different preparation and scanning parameters. For **SSSA** and **VELLUM**, no existing data will be used as the data are strictly connected to the used hardware and laser systems, accordingly. **HUJI** will apply past accomplishments of the laboratory to design the hydrogels. The pre-existing methods will guide the development of new hydrogel materials. For **ACMIT**, depending on material development and the identified clinical application, existing anatomical data and material data will be used for the generation of the testing platforms.

DATA SIZE & UTILITY

The expected size of the MAPWORMS data varies, from few MB (e.g., distributional data, images, videos) to several GB (e.g., micro-CT datasets). Specifically, 81 micro-CT scans have been generated with a total size of 2.43TB. Each micro-CT dataset available for download through the micro-CT vlab will be approximately 200-300 MB.

Concerning data utility, researchers from several disciplines will be interested. Distributional data derived by **CoNISMa** will offer updated biodiversity checklists of annelids in Italian seas for the Scientific Committee for the Fauna of Italy and for Marine Protected Areas (e.g., Marine Protected Area of Porto Cesareo, Marine Protected Area of Torre Guaceto) and the Apulia Region as required by Italian and European Directives. Molecular data will be useful for building DNA barcode libraries for environmental DNA metabarcoding purposes. Morphological and behavioral data will be useful for MAPWORMS researchers for the development of the annelids modelling. All the aforementioned data will be also useful for annelids taxonomists and ecologists outside the consortium. Despite the taxonomical and ecological interest, the micro-CT data can be used by academics and students for educational purposes, artists and animators for artistic purposes or experts in micro-CT technology for the investigation of digitization protocols and methods. Data derived by **HUJI** and **SSSA** will be of broad interest in diverse scientific disciplines, including drug-delivery,

sensing, actuation, materials science, robotics, and nanoparticles. Additionally, **VEXLUM**'s laser system with improved system performance, compact modular design and higher efficiency, could be of interest to the developers of medical technology or other application fields.

2.1 BIOLOGICAL DATA

2.1.1. INTRODUCTION

A crucial first step for the successful output of the MAPWORMS project is related to the taxonomy, behavior, and ecology of Annelida. A dedicated WP, in particular the WP2 – Ecological, taxonomical and morphological studies for selected species of marine Annelida aims to provide a solid biological background for WP3, WP4 and WP5. Specifically, CoNISMa and HCMR perform behavioral, ecological, taxonomical, morphological, and anatomical studies aimed at characterizing the identity, ecological and biological traits of Annelida species.

The results of this WP are the generation of five different types of data which belong to the general category of Biological Data (Table 1):

- a) Distributional/ georeferenced data
- b) Genomic data
- c) Morphological data
- d) Behavioral data
- e) Micro CT data

In particular, **CoNISMa** is responsible for seasonal sampling. Among the collected specimens, a part has been stored for micro-CT analysis carried out by HCMR, a part has been used for integrated morphological/molecular taxonomic analysis, and a part has been maintained alive in the aquarium facilities of CoNISMa Unit at the University of Salento for rearing experiments. From the aforementioned activities, biological data are generated (e.g., images, videos, DNA sequences, taxonomical data). Biological data (e.g., 3D images, videos) related to the Annelids morphology, have been also generated by **HCMR** using the micro-CT technology.

A. DISTRIBUTIONAL/ GEOREFERENCED DATA

CoNISMa has submitted metadata and data from the sampling campaigns to OBIS and in particular to the dedicated node for the Mediterranean Region, which is MedOBIS (<http://medobis.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>). MedOBIS includes data for the Mediterranean Sea from a wide range of references and time periods and it is

encompassed within the framework of OBIS Nodes. It is hosted by the Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology and Aquaculture (IMBBC, <https://imbbsc.hcmr.gr/>) of the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR, <https://www.hcmr.gr/en/>). Since EMODNET (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en>) and LifeWatchGreece (<https://www.lifewatchgreece.eu/>) projects, MedOBIS started operating as a Tier 2 Node. The main principle of MedOBIS is the contribution to science with FAIR and OPEN data. All the data are published through an Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT), <http://ipt.medobis.eu/>, harvested by OBIS. The IPT provides the ability to assign DOIs to datasets by using a DataCite account, creating a data repository. The IPT is an open-source software tool, freely available by the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) network.

For distributional/ georeferenced data, a metadata template accompanies every sampling event, in order to collect as much information as possible. This metadata template is presented in ANNEX III. The relevant data are sent to the MedOBIS Data Management Team in HCMR to be standardized, quality controlled, and finally uploaded and published to the MedOBIS Repository, under CC-BY License.

The Salento Peninsula has been selected as the source of the biological material collected due to its geographical position and environmental variability, which offers a wide array of potential model species within a relatively restricted area. Information about the marine annelid fauna occurring along the Salento Peninsula coastline (Italy) was obtained by two sources: a) from data mining the available literature, focusing on papers dealing with community ecology and annelid taxonomy, and b) from new sampling events.

The outcome of data mining is two separate datasets, one with georeferenced records of annelid species and one including non-georeferenced literature reporting annelid species along the Salento peninsula. Both datasets are organized based on Darwin Core Standards and its metadata are available through MedOBIS repository. See ANNEX V for more details on Darwin core standards used. The literature datasets were also uploaded into MAPWORMS Zenodo community, without any access restrictions (links: <https://zenodo.org/records/7869994> and <https://zenodo.org/records/7869960>).

During the first year of the MAPWORMS project (between 01/05/2022 and 28/02/2023), approximately 40 sampling events were organized in different habitat and at different depths to obtain new distributional data about marine annelids along the Salento peninsula. The sampling events were organized to cover areas and environments scarcely investigated in published literature. Whenever possible, the sampled specimens were photographed alive. The dataset of new annelid occurrences also followed the Darwin Core Standards and its metadata are available through MedOBIS repository. The dataset was uploaded into MAPWORMS Zenodo community (link: <https://zenodo.org/records/7870065>) but, as many of these data might be of interest for further publications it has been subjected to an embargo time (until April 30, 2025) and will be made publicly available after the publication of these data in a peer-reviewed journal.

The gathered georeferenced distributional data allowed to reconstruct a distributional map of marine annelids along the coasts of Salento, highlighting in particular the occurrence of well-studied and scarcely studied areas and marine systems. This map, along with interesting taxonomic and statistical biological information, is available through MAPWORMS Zenodo community (link: <https://zenodo.org/records/8039801>).

B. GENOMIC DATA

Material sampled during the project has been preserved for genetic analyses and once processed will be deposited in the “Museo di Biologia Marina” of Porto Cesareo. DNA extraction was carried out with a cost- and time-effective salting-out protocol on a small fragment of tissue, taking care of not damaging any diagnostic character on the preserved annelid. DNA was extracted from 422 individuals belonging to 202 morphospecies. Genetic characterization was obtained through two mitochondrial markers (the genes coding for the subunit I of the cytochrome c oxidase and the 16S rRNA); these markers were chosen as they are widely used in species delimitation of animals, and a good amount of data on marine annelids is available in public repositories. Useful sequences of at least one of the two markers were obtained for 143 morphospecies, while for the remaining 78 species sequences were not readable even in case of apparently successful amplification.

Regarding genomic data, the potential repositories that could be used are presented in ANNEX IV. Most common are ENA and GenBank, but also Barcode of Life Data System (BOLD) is considered suitable and is used for the purposes of the current project. BOLD is an online workbench and database that supports the assembly and use of DNA barcode data. Thus, all sequences obtained were uploaded to BOLD together with the metadata of the corresponding individuals within the project “MAPWORMS – Mimicking Adaptations and Plasticity in WORMS”, under embargo until the planned publication of the results.

C. MORPHOLOGICAL AND D. BEHAVIORAL DATA

Data regarding annelid morphology, such as measurements, pictures, drawings belong to morphological data. Annelid measurements have been submitted to Zenodo MAPWORMS community (<https://zenodo.org/records/13897604>) and at a later stage can be standardized and submitted also in MedOBIS, following the same procedure as distributional/ georeferenced data. Whenever possible, there will be a link in the MedOBIS Repository to connect distributional/ georeferenced data with the related morphological data, through the OBIS-ENV data format. This format is based on the Darwin Core Archive (DwC-A, <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>) standard for biodiversity and aims to capture all measurements related to habitat features, such as physical and chemical variables of the environment, and biotic measurements (such as body size, abundance, biomass, etc).

Regarding the morphological data derived from the 2D/3D analysis of the micro-CT data, these refer to the morphological description of the *Phascolosoma* (*Phascolosoma*)

stephensoni (Sipuncula) and *Glycera tridactyla* (Polychaeta) specimens which have been selected as model species for the creation of the bio-inspired robot. In these scans, 2D and 3D analysis (e.g., volume, length of muscles, structure thickness etc) are being performed, allowing for the characterization of several parameters for modelling the worms and inspire the final robot. Datasets derived from the final analysis will be uploaded when ready in the [MAPWORMS Zenodo community](#) under embargo until the release of the relevant publication.

As far as it concerns behavioral data, these refer to annelid behavior (footages, video formats, ethograms etc.). These data might inspire technical concepts potentially worth patenting and thus should be treated with care and maybe released after proper authorization by the IM and the IMB.

The first measurements for the two main categories of potential model organisms which have been identified, and in particular the unsegmented Annelida (Sipuncula, Echiura) and Annelida with eversible, armed pharynx (Phyllodoceida, Eunicida) are presented in the Deliverable D2.2 "First set of parameters for modelling". Standardized measurements of the external anatomy were performed on live individuals of *Phascolosoma stephensoni* in narrow aquaria filled with seawater using videos. In particular, frames from videos were analysed with the software ImageJ to obtain accurate measurements of the length and radius of the animals. After the characterization of the length and radius of the worms, additional tests were carried out to evaluate the speed of worms when moving in the aquaria filled with 0.5% agarose gel. The digging behavior of the worm in the filled aquaria was filmed.

Figure 3. Experimental video set-up used for the characterization of worms.

All the aforementioned measurements are provided through the Deliverable 2.2. which is uploaded in Zenodo and will be openly available when it is approved by the EU after the review process.

E. MICRO CT DATA

Up to September 2024, 51 specimens belonging to Polychaeta and Sipuncula have already been scanned using the Skyscan 1172 micro-CT at HCMR to visualize their morphological

and anatomical characteristics. From these specimens, 81 micro-CT scans have been generated, as many specimens were scanned both with and without contrast agents to visualize different structures (e.g., dense structures need to be scanned without contrast agents). All datasets, along with their metadata, will be stored and uploaded to the Micro-CT virtual laboratory (<https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>). This virtual lab offers to the user a collection of virtual 3D specimens which are annotated with metadata and can be interactively displayed and retrieved through a web-based application.^[2] MicroCTvlab has also an API (Application Programming Interface) in order to allow the user to get information on various microCT data scans, species information, and metadata related to the microCT dataset scans. A new collection for the MAPWORMS microCT scans has been created in the microCTvlab which is called MAPWORMS, in which all relative microCT scans will be uploaded (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The MAPWORMS specimen collection of the microCT scans.

In the MAPWORMS collection an example of a microCT scan can be found in <https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/node/89>. By selecting the microCT dataset, the user has the ability to: a) see a short description of the scan with relative images, b) interact with the 3D representation of the sample using the web based Slice:Drop (<https://slicedrop.com/>) software, c) see a relative video of the scan and d) display the metadata for the dataset (Figure 5). Raw data can be downloaded by the metadata tab in .nifti format (nii.gz). Images (in .png, .gif, .jpg or .jpeg format) and videos (in .mp4 format) can be also downloaded from the metadata tab.

Figure 5. Features on the microCTvlab.

All data mentioned in sections A-E above, and in particular distributional/ georeferenced, genomic, morphological and micro-CT data will be openly available to interested users after an embargo period, which is estimated to be until the end of April 2025, mainly depending on the publications foreseen by the participating partners. All protocols used for these data types will be clearly described in the selected repositories (microCTvlab, BOLD, Zenodo) and publications. However, data that might be characterized sensitive due to their direct inspiration for potentially patentable technical concepts (WP6), e.g., behavioral data, needs to be handled according to the MAPWORMS Internal Committee. In the framework of FAIR principles, for any sensitive data, it is proposed to submit and immediately publish at least their relevant metadata.

2.2 TECHNICAL DATA

Apart from Biological Data presented in the previous section, and referred to WP2 activities, technical data will also be part of the MAPWORMS project. Technical data consist of five different types of data (Table 1), which are:

- a. Modelling data
- b. Laser characterization data
- c. Anatomical modelling data

- d. Experimental data
- e. Morphing data

A. MODELLING DATA

Modelling data, such as codes, software, mechanical simulations, and images are being produced according to WP3. WP3 aims at developing theoretical and numerical tools to model the shape changes of thin sheets driven by the modulation of internal stresses and stiffness variations (algorithmic morphing). The shape changing capabilities of these thin sheets are inspired by the shape changing capabilities of marine Annelida, and form the basis of the design of worm-inspired robots based on stimuli-responsive materials with controllable stiffness.

Modelling data are coming from: dedicated characterization/design process (i.e., mechanical/visual characterization through i) Instron material testing machine, ii) load cells, iii) Hyrox); software for realization process through specific machines (soft materials 3D printer, laser cutter); simulation software; CAD design. Data are strictly connected to the used hardware and in the specific project dedicated systems (gel or characterization set ups) are created. The tools that can be used in order to access these types of data come mainly with a fee (MATLAB, LabVIEW, CAD software, COMSOL), but there are some open-source softwares such as Arduino and Repetier-Host. Modelling data would be available through open access publications, as well as through an open access repository such as GitHub and Zenodo (ANNEX IV).

To reproduce some of the behaviors of Sipuncula and similar marine worms, it is considered helpful to model them in a way that is simple enough to be translated into the design and optimization of an artificial device, that is, models that can cover the gap between biology and technology. To do this, the **SSSA** team building on what has been presented in Deliverable D2.2 “First set of parameters for modelling” and D3.1 “Validated morphing algorithm for smart hydrogels based on non-Euclidean plates”, has developed a 3D model based on the notion of multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient, that can be adopted to mimic worm behaviors by means of actively imposing a target 3D metric tensor. This mechanism is particularly useful as it can be easily adapted to different actuation strategies and it is presented in D3.2 “Validated direct morphing FEM algorithms”, which will be openly available at [Zenodo MAPWORMS community](#) by the end of 2024.

B. LASER CHARACTERISATION DATA

In parallel, technical data in the form of datasheets will be generated by VEXLUM, during the process of characterization of the laser systems. VEXLUM has an increasing exposure to quantum technology, semiconductor metrology, and laser medicine applications, where OEM lasers with specific wavelengths requirements (some of them overlapping with

MAPWORMS targets) are in high demand, particularly when it comes to the ability to tailor the wavelengths and ensure a compact form factor and cost-effectiveness. An example of a laser characterization report (datasheet) is openly available in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/13939007>).

C. ANATOMICAL MODELLING DATA

In addition to the modelling data used for computer simulation generated in WP3, **ACMIT** is also using and generating modelling data for the development of appropriate testing environments in WP6, which will be anatomical models (also called phantoms) for proposed medical use-cases. These anatomical modelling data includes data of the human anatomy, which is taken from segmented medical images. In the current project, only available data will be used – from previous projects at ACMIT or online repositories. In addition, data on material properties (of human tissue and artificial materials) is needed, similar to mechanical property data in the computer simulation. This data will be taken from literature or previously performed material tests. Based on the anatomy and material data, models will be designed using 3D Slicer and CAD-Software (e.g., Solidworks, Fusion 360) and – depending on the fabrication method (3D-printing or molding) – g-Code files for 3D-printing will be generated, either directly for the parts or for corresponding molds.

D. EXPERIMENTAL DATA

WP4 deals with Experimental data, including the synthesis and characterization of stimuli-responsive hydrogels. Past accomplishments and experience of HUJI laboratory are applied to design the hydrogels. The pre-existing methods guide the development of the new hydrogel materials. These data will be well described through publications envisaged. Experimental data will be stored in Zenodo, as it is shown in ANNEX IV.

HUJI's detailed experimental results and scientific accomplishments have been published in high-impact open access articles.⁽⁵⁾ HUJI has already developed novel methods to assemble stimuli-responsive cryogels. The scientific efforts and results were summarized in an open-access publication,⁽⁶⁾ acknowledging the MAPWORMS European project. This publication is available at MAPWORMS Zenodo community: [Stiffness-Switchable, Biocatalytic pH-Responsive DNA-Functionalized Polyacrylamide Cryogels and their Mechanical Applications \(zenodo.org\)](#). In this publication, the large-pore interconnected channels morphology of cryogels demonstrated to lead to enhanced chemical reactions and control over physical properties compared to analogous hydrogel matrices, which are dominated by a closed small porous structure. In addition, HUJI developed methods to assemble stimuli-responsive, dissipative, transient stiffness, functional hydrogel matrices. The scientific efforts and results were summarized in an open-access publication,⁽⁷⁾ [Chemical and Photochemical-Driven Dissipative Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺-Ion Cross-Linked Carboxymethyl Cellulose Gels Operating Under Aerobic Conditions: Applications for Transient Controlled Release](#)

[and Mechanical Actuation \(zenodo.org\)](#), acknowledging the MAPWORMS European project. In this work, HUJI demonstrated chemical and light-induced temporal, transient release of loads and transient mechanomorphing functions, showcasing the potential use of the dissipative Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺-Ion crosslinked CMC for soft robotic applications.

E. MORPHING DATA

In WP5, **SSSA** evaluates responsivity to stimulation gradients in order to optimally mimic biological organism reaction to the environment, thus inspiring real morphing adaptation of future robots overcoming the traditional approach based on bi-stable behaviours. Robot ability to adapt and react to the environment will also be tested in order to reach different research fields, e.g., environmental application. These data are considered as Morphing data of this project and will be stored in Zenodo (ANNEX IV).

This project aims at developing worm-inspired soft robots with modular architecture by combining various actuation units capable of simple primitive movements, and responsive to stimuli such as magnetic fields, temperature and pressure changes, pH variations, and chemical reactions. The Deliverable 5.2 "First version of actuation units' combination" outlined the development of magnetic-responsive and temperature-responsive actuation units. Magnetic-responsive bending and twisting actuation units have been designed and characterized under different magnetic field intensities and directions. These units demonstrate potential applications in achieving peristaltic-type motions and fluidic transmission mechanisms able to mimic the functionalities of the hydrostatic skeleton in worms. However, permanent magnets were used for the actuation, resulting in different magnetic field applied along the structure of the actuation units. In the future, an electromagnetic coil system would be used for actuation, ensuring uniform magnetic fields and gradients in the workspace under analysis. ACMIT is supporting the development of fluidic systems by the preparation of hemispheric fluidic actuation units using their custom silicone 3D-printer.

Moreover, temperature-responsive actuation units with variable stiffness have been developed. These units consist of bilayer structures combining pH-responsive hydrogels with thermo-responsive polymers. The reversible stiffness changes in response to pH changes or redox reactions enable diverse mechano-morphing functionalities, offering possibilities for controlled material transport and load release.

Further investigations will involve the optimization of the smart and modular architecture, combining the described actuation units, aiming at achieving worm-inspired robots with enhanced motility and functionality. Future developments will also include the combination of different actuation units into complex architectures. The Deliverable 5.2 will be openly available at [Zenodo MAPWORMS community](#) by the end of 2024.

Some technical data, which may be considered sensitive for potential patenting, may request a specified embargo period, but in the framework of FAIR principles, this period will be reduced as much as possible.

2.3 PATENT-SEARCH DATA

In WP6, an extensive patent search is performed by **ACMIT**, resulting in patent-search data in the area of research, in particular regarding the actuation mechanisms defined in WP3 and WP4, as well as different kinds of robots evolving from those, explored in WP5, and potential applications in medical technology, defined in WP6. As the partners SSSA and HUJI have the main knowledge in these fields, the keywords for the searches are collected in close cooperation with those partners.

In D6.1 – Preliminary IP report, a first overview was given on available patents in a very broad, project related research field. During the project, the research field is narrowed and more specific searches are carried out, resulting in an updated mid-project overview at the second review-meeting and a final IP report at the end of the project. Basic research is performed in Google Patent and Espacenet, while an AI-supported tool (PATOffice) is used to keep track. The patent - search data is kept restricted for the public.

2.4 DISSEMINATION DATA

Dissemination data are referring to any information obtained during the MAPWORMS project and disseminated through social media, its official website and the scientific publications. According to D1.2 (MAPWORMS_D1.2_project handbook_v5_20220729), when results (e.g., presentation, article, etc.) obtained within a WP are intended to be published by a partner, the WP leader and the IM have to be informed. Furthermore, the Article 17 in the MAPWORMS Grant Agreement mentions that *“a beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.”* A comprehensive list of the dissemination data can be found in D1.4 – Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and in D1.5 & D.1.8 – Annual reports on key communication events.

Dissemination data can be also related to those used in exhibitions or in web platforms and mobile applications. For example, micro-CT data have been disseminated through a touchscreen monitor using the DrishtiPrayog open source software at the [InnoDays](#) innovation exhibition during 24-26 November 2023, organized by the Region of Crete (Figure 7). These data may also be disseminated using this software at the Cretaquarium at the end of the project.

Figure 7. Micro-CT datasets disseminated at the Innodays exhibition.

Micro-CT data will be also disseminated through a mobile web application developed on Wordpress CMS with the use of the Web Apps (PWA) plugin (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Mobile application for the dissemination of micro-CT data

3 FAIR DATA

MAPWORMS supports the concept of FAIR data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) and for this reason invests towards offering its research data as FAIR data.

ANNEX IV lists some potential (European and non-European) data repositories for redistribution of the thematic data types generated within MAPWORMS. It is noted, that apart from the patent-search data, also the data regarding annelid behavior (footages, ethograms, video formats, etc.) might be considered as sensitive for potential patenting purposes and could be available at the end of the project and after proper authorization by the MAPWORMS Internal Committee. Finally, the used protocols will be described in detail in the selected repositories and in publications in order to increase visibility and reproducibility for any interested users.

It is worth mentioning, that special effort was focused on increasing the FAIRness status of Micro CT data. This effort is described in the publication entitled "Applying FAIR principles to Micro-CT data, the case of MAPWORMS PROJECT", presented at the 5th International Congress on Applied Ichthyology, Oceanography, and Aquatic Environment (HydroMediT 2024).^[7]

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

In order to ensure the findability of all produced data by the MAPWORMS project, the following four principles (F1-F4) are supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide:^[3]

F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier: all repositories proposed in the ANNEX IV are using globally unique and persistent identifiers (Digital Object Identifier - DOI) in order to remove ambiguity. An exception is the micro-CTvlab which does not assign DOIs. However, this repository is hosted at the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research which keeps it active over time - through its Network Operations Center (NOC). Furthermore, each dataset uploaded in the micro-CTvlab has been assigned with a unique identifier resulting in a unique URL for each dataset.

F2. Data are described with rich metadata: MAPWORMS project datasets will be described with rich metadata (descriptive information about the data). All partners are encouraged to be generous and extensive when providing metadata information. The concept is that even if the data are not available, at least they are described by rich metadata.

The proposed repositories in ANNEX IV, have mandatory metadata fields that need to be filled. For example, Zenodo, which is being used as a repository for several types of datasets, has a standard metadata catalogue which will guide the partners for the appropriate metadata fields. Regarding the microCT datasets, there are no metadata standards,

however the micro-CTvlab offers an extensive list of rich metadata (ANNEX VI) with mandatory metadata fields.

According to the Article 17 of the MAPWORMS grant agreement, metadata of the deposited publications should be licensed under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or equivalent, and provide information at least about the following:

- a. publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue)
- b. Horizon Europe funding
- c. grant project, name, acronym and number
- d. licensing terms
- e. persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant.
- f. persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication (where applicable)

In the case of metadata of deposited data, these must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded) in accordance with Article 17. Furthermore, these metadata should provide information at least about the following:

- a) datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo)
- b) Horizon Europe funding
- c) grant project name, acronym and number
- d) licensing terms
- e) persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant
- f) persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs (where applicable)

F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe:

metadata and the dataset they describe are usually separate files, thus the association between a metadata file and the dataset should be made explicit by mentioning the dataset globally unique and persistent identifier in the metadata.

F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource: datasets will be uploaded in well-known repositories (see ANNEX IV).

Naming conventions are very important as consistent naming increases the findability of the project data. The D1.2 (MAPWORMS_D1.2_project handbook_v5_20220729) has set up the rules for the naming convention of the work package and deliverable reports (Table 2). Datasets names should also be consistent as it is indicated in the following Table 2. Version numbers will be clear in each uploaded dataset. Each partner will be responsible to upload the updated versions of their datasets with the appropriate naming convention

and the appropriate version number. Relative keywords should also be provided based on the naming conventions and the metadata. *MAPWORMS datasets available in Zenodo MAPWORMS community were standardised according to MAPWORMS naming conventions and were enriched with metadata records in accordance with the Article 17 of the MAPWORMS grant agreement.*

Table 2 MAPWORMS naming conventions

TYPE OF DOCUMENT	NAME OF THE FILE
Work package report or other project	MAPWORMS_WP[xx]_[kindofreport]_[shorttitle]_rev[xx]_yyyymmdd
Deliverable report	MAPWORMS_D[xx]_[shorttitle]_rev[xx]_yyyymmdd
Data files	MAPWORMS_PartnerName_[shorttitle]_version number[xx]_yyyymmdd

3.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

MAPWORMS data can be accessed and explored using various software tools. Most of these data are provided in formats that can be accessed and used through open-source software. In particular, MedOBIS for georeferenced data uses the Integrated Publishing Tool, which is a free open-source software developed by GBIF and used by organizations around the world to create and manage repositories for sharing biodiversity datasets. Regarding micro-CT data, MicroCT vLab uses the Slice-Drop, which is an open-source, interactive visualization tool that allows users to visualize imaging data in three dimensions. In addition, Zenodo is an open repository that allows for sharing and preserving data of any size and format. Zenodo code is also open source, built on the open source [Invenio](#) digital library. Furthermore, metadata in Zenodo are available under CC0 licence, and all open content is accessible through open APIs.

During the project life, according to Table 1, non-open-source software is also used (e.g., Dragonfly software, for which there is a free license for researchers with non-commercial activities). Though, the outcomes of the analysis that will be deposited in Zenodo will be openly accessible.

To ensure the accessibility of all produced data by the MAPWORMS project, the following two principles (A1-A2) are supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide ^[3]:

A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol: Most partners will use http(s) or ftp. A well-organized documentation system and a fully mechanized protocol will ensure freely accessible data. Sensitive data will be guaranteed as FAIR by providing contact details of the data responsible. These details will be explicitly included in the metadata.

A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available: This DMP targets to relate to well-known and well-maintained repositories. Nevertheless, in cases of data unavailability, it is crucial to be able to trace people, institutions or publications associated with the original research. Therefore, this DMP emphasizes the necessity of Metadata availability.

In particular in Zenodo, all metadata is stored in JSON-format and can be exported in several standard formats (e.g.MARCXML, Dublin Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema; according to the OpenAIRE Guidelines.

According to the D1.2 (MAPWORMS_D1.2_project handbook_v5_20220729), five types of documents will be produced according to their dissemination and confidentiality level:

- PU – Public, fully open, e.g., web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Currently, apart from public data, [the MAPWORMS Zenodo Community](#) hosts also embargoed data and data with restricted access. The target is all the aforementioned data to be openly available at the latest by the end of the project. MAPWORMS' DM will continuously monitor the project results in order to define the correct strategy for data sharing throughout the project duration. The program will maintain balance between the IP and Open access strategies of the data through constant communication with the IM, the IMB and the DM.

Regarding scientific publications, in general, MAPWORMS project supports, where possible, an Open Access Strategy based on the Guidelines about the rules on Open Access to Scientific publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020 (Figure).

Following the aforementioned guidelines, here are the subsequent options for the scientific publications:

a) Self-archiving/ “green” open access, in which the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript can be deposited in an online repository before, at the same time or after the publication. In some cases, open access can be granted after an embargo period.

b) Open access publishing/ “gold” open access, in which the articles will be immediately published as open access with no publication costs for the subscribers. The university/research institute/agency funding the research, covers the publication costs. In other cases, the costs of open access publishing are covered by subsidies or other funding models.

MAPWORMS project aims to publish the project results as “gold” open access in order to increase the accessibility of the obtained results. When the “gold” open access publishing is not applicable (e.g., conference proceedings or abstract), the “green” open access will be adopted where authors can make pre-prints available to the wider community.

Currently, [the MAPWORMS Zenodo Community](#) hosts 5 posters, 1 presentation and 4 publications, all of which are gold open access.

Figure 9 Open access strategy for the access and reuse of research data. Modified image from [4]

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

In order to make the MAPWORMS data interoperable the following three principles (I1-I3) are supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide:^[3]

I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. In other words, it should be possible for people and computers to interpret both metadata and data of the project and be able to combine it with other datasets. This principle prerequisites to include proper documentation while making your data available, use preferred and common file formats and clear dataset structures. All the aforementioned are achieved through the use of repositories such as Zenodo and file formats (see Table 1) that are acceptable and commonly used through the research community.

I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles. MAPWORMS partners use controlled vocabularies, such as Darwin Core Standards for transmitting information about biodiversity and Marine Regions for localities, to describe their datasets. These vocabularies use globally unique and persistent identifiers (e.g., links).

I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data. In this case, any partner should specify if any dataset is built on another dataset or additional datasets/ information are needed for data description. For this reason, MAPWORMS partners add any relative links between the different datasets.

In this context, all datasets are properly cited (i.e., including their globally unique and persistent identifiers), and use controlled vocabularies and ontologies, such as Darwin Core standards for distributional data. The Darwin Core standard includes a glossary of terms intended to facilitate the sharing of information about biological diversity by providing identifiers, labels, and definitions.

Other examples of controlled vocabularies and ontologies, are: a) the WoRMS taxonomic mapping (<https://www.marinespecies.org/index.php>), which is an authoritative classification and catalogue of marine species names maintained at the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ); and b) the Marine Regions application (<https://www.marineregions.org/>), which is a standard list of marine georeferenced place names and areas.

3.4 INCREASE DATA RE-USE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENCES)

In order to optimize the reuse of the produced data by the MAPWORMS project from any interested user, the following principle (R1) is supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide:^[3]

R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes: each data owner should provide rich metadata which describe all the aspects of the data generation (e.g., experimental protocols followed, species used, search keywords etc.). In this framework, the metadata fields for Micro CT are updated and include

new obligatory information related to citation, data license, dataset url, publication date, scientificNameID (see ANNEX VI).

Furthermore, in order to increase the discoverability of the data, a clear licensing status is important for the users and the machines. For this reason, MAPWORMS DMP supports the Creative Commons License. There are several types of Creative Commons licenses which differ regarding the terms of data distribution. For MAPWORMS metadata the proposed license would be Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC0). CC0 allows the users to freely build upon, enhance and reuse the MAPWORMS metadata without restriction under copyright or database law. For further details see Chapter 3.1.

For MAPWORMS data, the options would be: a) CC BY, which allows the reuse of data (and for commercial use) with the appropriate credit; b) CC BY-NC, which allows the reuse of data (not for commercial use) with the appropriate credit; and c) CC BY-SA, which allows the reuse of data (and for commercial use) with the appropriate credit and the modified data should be licensed under identical terms.

MAPWORMS data will be openly available for re-use to interested users after an embargo period, which will be estimated mainly depending on the publications foreseen by the participating partners and when the potential patents have been filed.

To stimulate discovery and potential re-use of the metadata and data, MAPWORMS maximally exploits existing data flow pathways to share data through well-known European e-infrastructures, such as EMODnet and global initiatives like OBIS and GBIF.

4 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Data management is included in WP1. Ms Dimitra Mavraki was appointed as a Data Manager (DM) for the Data Management Plan (DMP) handling during the MAPWORMS kickoff meeting, on the 13th of May 2022, in Pisa. Ms Dimitra Mavraki is an Environmental Scientist with post-graduate studies on Hydrology and Environmental Management of Water Resources. She has been working as Data Manager at the HCMR, since 2013. She is specialized in marine data collection and digitization, quality control and standardization of both new and historical data, FAIR Principles to marine (meta)data, open access E-infrastructures and Repositories. She has 17 relevant publications and in 2019 she was a Grant winner as an expert European Researcher & Scientist working with data to attend the 14th Research Data Alliance Plenary meeting, in Helsinki, under the theme "Data Makes the Difference". The role of DM is to work closely with each partner in order to guide on how to make MAPWORMS data FAIR. Besides the management of produced data, mainly allocated by HCMR, all the partners have allocated a dedicated budget for handling and disseminating their data.

During the project, MAPWORMS data are going to be linked to the key European integrating data infrastructures and repositories (EMODnet, MedOBIS, BOLD, Zenodo, MicroCT-vlab)

which provide long-term preservation of the data. Further details about the selected repositories can be found in ANNEX IV.

5 DATA SECURITY

MAPWORMS website (<https://www.mapworms.eu/>) is hosted on the Aruba provider (<https://www.aruba.it/>) which adopts the following protection measures:

- *Anti-DDoS protection.* The DDoS attack is fought by analyzing incoming data, detecting abnormal traffic and, where possible, blocking potentially dangerous packages.
- *Firewalls and WAFs.* Servers' firewalls protect machines' access ports from unauthorized external connections.
- *IDS systems.* Thanks to Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), the website is constantly monitored from potentially harmful calls in order to intervene with appropriate precautionary blocking measures.
- *Blocking malicious IPs.* Constant monitoring of the main blacklists permits to pre-emptively block any attempts to access your site from any of the reported IP addresses.

Regarding data security and website integrity, these backups are made:

- the provider automatically makes a daily and a weekly backup hosted in the space used for the website and accessible only by ftp;
- a manual backup is performed by the SSSA team every month and stored on a device disconnected from the network.

As reported in the D1.1 (MAPWORMS_D1.1_Website and Project LOGO_V4), MAPWORMS website is also exploitable as a gateway to a private repository platform for the Consortium and only available to registered partners. To protect the registered users' accounts and data from unauthorized access all users must systematically change their login password every 90 days.

Only the SSSA team can access the website storage area to upload reports, results data etc. This private area of the website does not allow for the modification of documents but only the possibility to upload (only by the SSSA team) and download (by the other registered users) of these documents.

Regarding, the **MicroCTvlab website** (<https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>) it is hosted on the HCMR provider (<https://www.hcmr.gr/>), which adopts the following protection measures:

- *Anti - DoS protection.* DDoS attacks are countered by examining incoming data, identifying unusual traffic, and blocking potentially harmful packets where feasible.
- *Firewalls.* Servers' firewalls protect internal networks from unauthorised external access.

- Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems (IDPS). These monitor network traffic for suspicious activities and potential threats, automatically alerting administrators or blocking access.
- Preventing access from harmful IPs. Continuous surveillance of key blacklists allows for proactively blocking any attempts to reach your site from flagged IP addresses.

Regarding data security and website integrity, HCMR provider automatically creates daily and weekly backups, stored in the space allocated for the website and accessible exclusively via FTP;

The MicroCTVlab website was developed using the Drupal CMS. To protect the website, the Drupal core and all modules were kept up to date. Additionally, security modules were used, including: Security Review Module: for performing automated security checks, Captcha and reCaptcha: to protect against bots and automated attacks, HoneyPot Module: which helps reduce form spam by adding hidden fields invisible to human users but capable of trapping bots and Password Policy: which enforces strong password requirements such as complexity, expiration, and reuse prevention.

The MAPWORMS project works in collaboration with the major ocean Data Research Infrastructures, which have the mandate for long-term data curation and preservation, such as EMODnet, and LifeWatch ERIC. Zenodo is also a safe certified repository as data are stored in CERN'S Data Centre and it is built and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE. Furthermore, the DM has created a dedicated [MAPWORMS community](#) in Zenodo which will increase the data curation through the acceptance or rejection of data input in the community collection. MAPWORMS results are recommended to be linked with the MAPWORMS Zenodo community. Details about the selected repositories can be found in ANNEX IV.

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

All ethical aspects of this project are covered in the Ethics Self-Assessment section (pages 21-22) in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Based on the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR- <https://gdpr.eu/>), project partners are responsible for the handling of personal data involved in their activities. MAPWORMS project will not transfer personal data to any other entities.

National legislation will be followed regarding sampling of species. National and European data protection regulations will be followed.

7 OTHER ISSUES

Nothing to report.

8 REFERENCES

- [1] Horizon 2020 FAIR Data Management Plan (DMP) Template. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-datamanagement/data-management_en.htm
- [2] Keklikoglou K, Faulwetter S, Chatzinikolaou E, Michalakis N, Filiopoulou I, Minadakis N, et al. (2016) Micro-CTvlab: A web based virtual gallery of biological specimens using X-ray microtomography (micro-CT). *Biodiversity Data Journal* 4: e8740. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.4.e8740>
- [3] Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., et al. (2016) The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- [4] Horizon 2020 Online Manual. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm
- [5] M. Fadeev et al., "Stimuli-Responsive DNA-Based Hydrogels on Surfaces for Switchable Bioelectrocatalysis and Controlled Release of Loads," *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, vol. 15, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.1021/acsami.3c06230
- [6] G. Davidson-Rozenfeld et al., "Stiffness-Switchable, Biocatalytic pH-Responsive DNA Functionalized Polyacrylamide Cryogels and their Mechanical Applications," *Adv. Funct Mater*, vol. 34, no. 4, p. 2306586, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1002/ADFM.202306586
- [7] Mavraki D., Kekikoglou K. (2024). Applying FAIR principles to Micro-CT data, the case of MAPWORMS project. *Proceedings of the 5th International Congress on Applied Ichthyology, Oceanography, and Aquatic Environment*, pp. 608–611, <https://hydromedit.gr/>

ANNEX I ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
ACMIT	Austrian Center for Medical Innovation and Technology
CoNISMa	Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Scienze del Mare
DM	Data Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EMODNET	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility

HCMR	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research
HUJI	Hebrew University of Jerusalem
IM	Innovation Manager
IMB	Innovation Management Board
IP	Intellectual Property
IPT	Integrated Publishing Toolkit
MedOBIS	Mediterranean Ocean Biogeographic Information System
OBIS	Ocean Biogeographic Information System
SSSA	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies
VEXLUM	Vexlum Ltd
WORMS	World Register of Marine Species
WP	Work Package

ANNEX II MAPWORMS DATA MANAGEMENT QUESTIONNAIRE TEMPLATE

MAPWORMS Data Management Questionnaire

Please provide your answers to the following questions considering your Institute/ Organization and the data or/and software which you will create or use during the project life.

For any questions you may have please contact Mrs. Dimitra MAVRAKI, dmavraki@hcmr.gr.

Send us your answers at dmavraki@hcmr.gr and keklikoglou@hcmr.gr by June 24th.

(Please give your answers in detail)

1. Data Summary

What types and formats of data are you going to generate/collect throughout the project?

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

What is the origin of your data?

What is the expected size of the data?

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

2. FAIR data

Will you keep metadata describing your data? What type of metadata (description, persons involved, protocols etc.)?

Your produced or used data in the project will be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

How will your data be made accessible (e.g., by deposition in a repository, which)?

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

2.3. Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How you want your data to be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Are you satisfied with CC-BY?

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Are data quality assurance processes described?

Metadata Format for submitted datasets

* *blue*: obligatory metadata field

* *white*: optional metadata field

Dataset title (= A descriptive title is necessary)	
Dataset citation (= Used to cite the dataset in future publications)	
Persons involved (= Define the persons involved and their specific role (indicate contact person))	
Abstract	
Keywords	
Publications (= Publications based on this dataset)	
Usage/ licence (= Specify if the dataset should be made available for public)	
Release date (=if left empty, dataset will immediately be available to the public, otherwise specify the date of release)	
External links (=Dataset already available elsewhere)	

Geographic coverage <i>(= Specify the location)</i>	
Taxonomic coverage <i>(= Specify the main taxonomic groups)</i>	
Funding and acknowledgments	
Equipment used	
Temporal coverage <i>(=First and last date of sampling)</i>	
Area sampled <i>(=Area sampled by equipment)</i>	
Number of stations	
Coordinates	
Number of Replicates <i>(= Per station/sample)</i>	
Habitat description	
Min/max depth	
Biomass present? <i>specify measuring method</i>	
Count present?	
Environ. variables present?	
Additional remarks	

ANNEX IV POTENTIAL (EUROPEAN AND NON-EUROPEAN) DATA REPOSITORIES FOR REDISTRIBUTION OF THE DATA TYPES WITHIN MAPWORMS PROJECT

Thematic data type category	Research domains	Potential data repositories for redistribution	URLs	Comments
Biodiversity data	e.g. biogeographic research, traits, taxonomy	- European Ocean Biogeographic Information System (EurOBIS) - Mediterranean Ocean Biogeographic Information System (MedOBIS) - Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) - Biology Portal of the European Marine Observation and Data Network	http://www.eurobis.org/ http://ipt.medobis.eu/ https://www.gbif.org/ http://www.emodnet.eu/biology	Data availability to OBIS under the following Creative Commons licenses: CC-0 CC-BY CC-BY-NC CC BY-SA In addition, shared datasets can be identified and cited through digital object identifiers (DOIs).
Genomic data	DNA Sequencing	- European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) - GenBank - BOLD SYSTEMS	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/ https://www.boldsystems.org/	BOLD shares a tightly integrated data exchange pipeline with NCBI (GenBank) that allows for automatic submission of data to GenBank.
Morphological Data		- Mediterranean Ocean Biogeographic Information System (MedOBIS) - Zenodo	http://ipt.medobis.eu/ https://zenodo.org/communities/mapworms/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest	
Behavioral data		-Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/communities/mapworms/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest	In Zenodo every upload is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Regarding license, users must specify it for all publicly available files. Licenses for closed access files may be specified in the description field.
Micro-CT data	e.g. Micro CT images, digital images, videos	-MicroCT vLab	- https://microct.portallifewatchgreece.eu/	This repository is hosted at the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research which keeps MicroCT vLab active over time through its NOC- Network Operations Center. The content of the microCT vlab is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)
Modelling data	e.g. software, codes	- GitHub - Zenodo	- https://github.com/	

			https://zenodo.org/communities/mapworms/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest	
Patent-search data	Evaluation list of prototypes	-Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/communities/mapworms/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest	

ANNEX V DARWIN CORE STANDARDS TERMS FOR BIOGEOGRAPHIC DATA

Darwin_core_term	Definition	Example
occurrenceID	A unique identifier for the occurrence record. This identifier is used to uniquely distinguish a specific occurrence (e.g., an observation or a specimen) from others in a dataset or across datasets.	mapworms:lit:coor:Annelida:1
basisOfRecord	Describes the type of record, such as whether it is an observation, a preserved specimen, or a machine-generated record. Common values include HumanObservation, PreservedSpecimen, FossilSpecimen, MaterialSample, and MachineObservation.	MaterialCitation
eventDate	The date or date range when the event (e.g., observation, collection) occurred. It should be formatted in ISO 8601 (e.g., YYYY-MM-DD).	2016-06-08
originalNameUsage	The original scientific name as it was used in the original source of the data. This can include older taxonomic names or variations that have since changed.	Hermodice carunculata
scientificName	The full scientific name of the organism, typically including genus and species (and sometimes additional taxonomic ranks such as subspecies or variety).	Hermodice carunculata (Pallas, 1766)
kingdom	The highest taxonomic rank of the organism in the biological classification system, representing a major group such as Animalia, Plantae, or Fungi.	Animalia
phylum	The taxonomic rank below kingdom and above class, grouping organisms based on general body plans and shared characteristics (e.g., Chordata for vertebrates).	Annelida
class	A taxonomic rank below phylum and above order, used to group organisms that share common characteristics (e.g., Mammalia for mammals).	Polychaeta
order	A taxonomic rank below class and above family, grouping organisms based on structural features and common ancestry (e.g., Carnivora for carnivorous mammals).	Amphinomida

family	A taxonomic rank below order and above genus, grouping closely related organisms (e.g., Felidae for cats).	Amphinomidae
genus	A taxonomic rank below family and above species, used to group species that are structurally similar or phylogenetically related (e.g., Panthera for big cats like lions and tigers).	Hermodice
specificEpithet	The second part of a binomial scientific name, identifying the species within the genus (e.g., in Homo sapiens, sapiens is the specific epithet).	carunculata
taxonRank	The taxonomic rank of the most specific name in the scientific name, such as species, subspecies, or variety.	species
habitat	The natural environment where the organism was found, describing the setting or type of environment (e.g., forest, desert, marine).	Rock
minimumDepthInMeters	The minimum depth (in meters) at which the organism was found or collected, relevant for aquatic or subterranean species.	60
maximumDepthInMeters	The maximum depth (in meters) at which the organism was found or collected, providing a range for its vertical habitat distribution.	70
decimalLatitude	The latitude of the location where the organism was found, expressed in decimal degrees. Positive values indicate north of the equator.	39,929583
decimalLongitude	The longitude of the location where the organism was found, expressed in decimal degrees. Positive values indicate east of the prime meridian.	18,4055
geodeticDatum	The reference system used for the geographic coordinates, ensuring accurate location data. Common datums include WGS84 and NAD83.	WGS84
country	The name of the country where the organism was found or collected, using the full official name (e.g., United States of America).	Italy
countryCode	The standardized code for the country where the organism was found, typically using ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 format (e.g., US for the United States).	IT
municipality	The name of the municipality or city where the organism was found, providing a more specific location within a country or region.	Tricase
locality	A detailed description of the specific location where the organism was found, often including landmarks, coordinates, or descriptive text.	Torre del Serpe

bibliographicCitation

A reference to a published work related to the occurrence, providing citation details such as authors, title, and publication date.

Micaroni V., et al. (2022) Project "Biodiversity MARE Tricase": A species inventory of the coastal area of Southeastern Salento. Diversity 14: 904.10.3390/d14110904

ANNEX VI MICRO CT UPDATED METADATA FIELDS

The screenshot displays the web interface for the species *Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni*. On the left, there are search filters for Scientific Name, Sample Type (Zoology, Annelida, Polychaeta, Eunicida, Lumbrineridae, Lumbrineris, Lumbrineris latreilli, Eunicidae, Eunice), Contrast Enhancement Method (HMDS, Iodine, None, PTA), and Project (BIOIMAGING-GR, ECCO, MAPWORMS). The main content area shows the Sample Category as Zoology / Annelida and tabs for General Info, 3D Visualization, Video, and Metadata. A 'Show less metadata' button is present. The metadata fields include:

- SpecimenID :** mCT-01334
- ScanID :** scan-01640
- Sample Category :** Zoology / Annelida
- Scientific Name :** *Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni*
- Scientific Name ID :** <https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=136081>
- Taxonomic Group :** ANNELIDA
- Provider Institute :** CONISMA
- Project :** MAPWORMS
- Funding :** European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme
- Project Info :** MAPWORMS project funded from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101046846
- Specimen Provider :** Luigi Musco
- Published by :** Hellenic Centre for Marine Research
- Publication Date :** Thu, 04/04/2024 - 11:30
- Material :** soft tissue
- Fixation Type :** formalin
- Preservation Medium :** Ethanol
- Contrast Enhancement Method :** Iodine
- Scope of Scan :** visualisation of retractor muscles
- Scan Date :** 12/19/2022
- Scanned By :** Niki Keklikoglou
- Sample Holder :** blue pipette tip

[SAMPLE TYPE](#) [API](#) [METADATA](#) [ABOUT](#) [OUR APP](#) [SEARCH](#) [CONTACT](#)

Search Filters

Scientific Name

Sample Type

Zoology
 -Annelida
 --Polychaeta
 ---Eunicida
 ----Lumbrineridae
 -----Lumbrineris
 -----Lumbrineris latreilli
 ----Eunicidae
 -----Eunice

Contrast Enhancement Method

HMDS
 Iodine
 None
 PTA

Project

BIOIMAGING-GR
 None
 ECCO
 MAPWORMS

Apply

Scanning Medium :	ethanol
Scanned Part :	whole specimen
Digital Device Type :	SkyScan 1172
Voltage kV :	50
Current uA :	199
Filter :	None
Zoom um :	6.89
Camera Resolution :	4000
ExposureTime (ms) :	946
360 :	180°
Random Movement :	0
Averaging :	3
Oversize Settings :	None
Dataset :	MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640_v1_20240404.nii_gz (239.29 MB)
Dataset URL :	https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/node/89
Micro-CT Images :	Download MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640image2_v1_20240404.png (393.43 KB) Download MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640image1_v1_20240404.png (551.78 KB)
Video File :	MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640_v1_20240404.mp4 (2.24 MB)
Data Licences :	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Data Owner :	Niki Keklikoglou
Citation :	Keklikoglou, K., Langeneck, J., Musco, L. (2024). Scan-01640.Micro-CTlab. https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/node/89

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